

5th E-NEWSLETTER | March 2024

We are excited to present to you the latest developments in our research endeavors in our second newsletter issue for 2024. Scroll down for an overview of all our activities and stay tuned for what lies ahead in the upcoming months.

Enjoy the read!

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NEWS

**2nd RECONMATIC Open Day in Manchester
Register Now!**

Open Day in Manchester, UK

May 7, 2024
09.00 - 17.00

**MediaCity campus -
University of Salford**

Funded by
the European Union

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The RECONMATIC partners are proud to invite you to a hybrid Open Day event about automated solutions for sustainable and circular construction and demolition waste management, that will take place on **May 7th, 2024**, at **MediaCity campus**.

Registration is now open for the four parallel interesting workshops along with presentations of the developed technologies, for this remarkable event, supported by CIRIA.

[Learn more](#)

Join Circular Construction Cluster

**CIRCULAR
CONSTRUCTION
CLUSTER**

Common elements, goals and identified potential synergies with several European initiatives, nurtured the idea of bringing them together to increase the impact of our results. In this direction, the RECONMATIC partners are excited to invite initiatives and projects working on circularity in construction to join the **Circular Construction Cluster**. Let's build a circular and sustainable construction sector together!

[Learn more](#)

National Workshops for construction stakeholders

The **RECONMATIC** national workshops aim to get feedback on the guidance and assessment tool developed within the project and to validate a selection of indicators to be implemented.

[Learn more](#)

100 participants in RECONMATIC Clustering Event

We invite you to watch the recording and read about the highlights of this successful clustering event, which included panel discussions to explore collaboration opportunities focused on circularity in construction among various research initiatives and projects.

[Learn more](#)

China endorsed the cooperation with RECONMATIC

The Chinese-European cooperation within the RECONMATIC project is now official, after the Chinese government approved the project proposal and signed the contract of the mission statement in December 2023.

[Learn more](#)

PUBLICATIONS

When Machine Learning Meets Raft: How to Elect a Leader over a Network

The paper was presented in the IEEE Globecom 2023, in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia and is referring to design and enhancements of “HyperLedger Fabric”, the open-source technology that uses blockchain to enable trackability and immutability.

[Learn more](#)

SYNERGIES

RECONMATIC joins the Tech4EUConstruction cluster

RECONMATIC joined in January 2024, the **Tech4EUconstruction cluster**, which is open to EU-funded projects working on AI and Robotics in Construction. Follow [#Tech4EUconstruction](#) on social media to stay tuned for the cluster’s latest activities and news.

[Learn more](#)

Assessing circularity in construction projects with CircularB

[Learn more](#)

MAELSTROM Smart technology for marine litter management

[Learn more](#)

Building on DECOMPOSE project for legislative reforms

[Learn more](#)

BLOG

The State of Excavation, Construction, and Demolition Waste (E.C.D.W.) in Cyprus

What are the reasons behind the disappointing facts and current practices in Cyprus? How is the new legislation going to affect the sector?

[Learn more](#)

WASTEie Journey #3: Implementing Information Management for Construction and Demolition Waste

About the integration of information requirements into established industry flows, focused on construction and demolition (C&D) waste management.

[Learn more](#)

EVENTS

**Morgan Sindall & BIMBox:
Embracing the Digital Frontier**

[Learn more](#)

**Visiting Futurebuild Expo 2024, by
Arcas & Callisto**

[Learn more](#)

**RECONMATIC in China
International Supply Chain Expo
2023**

[Learn more](#)

**Student challenge co-organised
with CIOB, Redrow Homes &
Liverpool John Moores University**

[Learn more](#)

Upcoming Activities

Register now at our hybrid [2nd Open Day Event](#), in Manchester, UK, on **7 May 2024**. Our UK partners have organised 4 engaging **workshops on waste management** addressed to all industry stakeholders.

Additionally, you will be able to meet the partners in the:

- **World Circular Economy Forum, WCEF2024, Brussels, 13-18 April 2024.** The representatives of the CACE
- **Net-Zero Future 2024 International Conference, Oslo, 19-21 June 2024** where the University of Salford will present a new scientific publication

Save the date and stay tuned via the project's social media channels on [LinkedIn \(@RECONMATIC\)](#) and [X \(Twitter\) \(@reconmatic\)](#) to never miss any updates on our activities!

[Subscribe](#) to our website to receive directly in your inbox all the updates about the deliverables and the papers soon to be published, as well as the project & clusters' activities and progress.

Tech4EUConstruction Cluster

BIM2TWIN Webinars

Learn about the Digital Building Twin platform, its applications and its testing on specific demonstration sites where physical building renovation or construction is happening.
Register now!

[Learn more](#)

BEEYONDERS “Meet our Tech”

Unveiling BEEYONDERS research on different topics. In [Meet our Tech #2](#) they present technologies on autonomous and teleoperated ground and aerial vehicles & [in Meet our Tech #3](#), additive manufacturing!

[Learn more](#)

Follow [#Tech4EUconstruction](#) on [LinkedIn](#) and [X \(Twitter\)](#) to stay tuned for the cluster's latest activities and news.

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